
THE ROLE OF CULTURAL AWARENESS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract.

The goal of teaching English as a second language is for students to be able to speak and write the language and comprehend the culture of the target language. Cultural content is regarded as essential as a means of instruction for enhancing language proficiency, cultural comprehension, and appreciation of diversity. The purpose of English textbooks was twofold: as language and cultural learning resources. The following are the findings:

1) The social materials were isolated into three kinds of source data.

2) The way of life materials were for the most part introduced into text as opposed to general media.

3) English textbooks contained four cultural components: products, practices, and perspectives of individuals

Students can develop character and moral values through cultural materials, enabling them to live and interact in a multicultural society.

Keywords.

Cultural awareness, globalization, consciousness, universal language, textbooks.

The fact that people are getting closer to one another does not come as a surprise as the rapid globalization that is taking place. As a result of the globalization of the world, there has been a significant shift in the ways in which we interact with one another. It is proverbial that a single tick on a site is sufficiently strong to keep individuals informed about the world. The digital-first strategy comes along with this change! We purchase things on the web, we talk on the web, we learn on the web! However, globalization is a multilevel process; As a result, it deserves careful consideration. At least, it offers us an interconnected world; As a result, people need to understand each other, respect each other's dignity, and be open to other worldviews.

Consciousness-raising educational practices are urgently required in light of the world's current situation, which includes a growing population that may lead to food and water insecurity and a decrease in other sources. Unity and harmony among humans are essential for ensuring a sustainable world; Consequently, educational practices ought to be structured to improve interpersonal relationships. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights states in Article 26:

The full development of the human personality and the improvement of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms should be the goals of education. It will advance the United Nations' efforts to maintain peace and foster understanding, tolerance, and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups. As a result, language classrooms are likely to take the lead in raising awareness of this issue! Given the worldwide place of English.

In this digital-first approach of the 21st century, it is reasonable to assert that there are distinct classes of English language speakers. English is not bound to any particular nation because it is a universal language. With the widespread adoption of English by non-native speakers, English teaching pedagogy ought to emphasize the importance of global issues. Through the promotion of intercultural awareness in language instruction, this could be accomplished.

Because textbooks are essential components of the language teaching pedagogy, they might be the wheels that turn the awareness of other cultures!

Therefore, it is of the utmost importance for the authors of textbooks to arrange the content in a manner that is responsive to the comprehension of intercultural differences. As a result, the purpose of this chapter is to provide a fresh perspective on intercultural understanding. It begins by demonstrating the significance of culture in language curriculum and then demonstrates how culture is used in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) textbooks.

At long last, the review closes by articulating the need to coordinate intercultural mindfulness into the language practices, and consequently ideas are given for material/educational plan designers about how it very well may be advanced. Murphy (1988) shows four ways to deal with social guidance in language homerooms: As a result, linguistic objectives come first in audio-visual methods, and culture is incorporated into language learning; There is no designated area for culture education. In terms of the communicative approach, culture contributes to successful communication. Culture, on the other hand, is extensively studied in Civilization modules, which combine language and culture. With respect to the intercultural approach, language is viewed as a necessary piece of the way of life,

and compassion between individuals is underscored. These words are echoed by Mar-Molinero (1992), who suggests that target language is frequently viewed as a problem through the prism of communicative language pedagogy. Because the learner is supposed to be a tourist who interacts with the target language, linguistic and functional strategies are required to resolve the issue. As a result, when we look at books that teach students how to communicate with people speaking the target language, we frequently find titles like "At the bus station," "At a restaurant," "How to ask for direction," and so on. These settings are exceptionally intended for language students to assist them with making due

in the objective language. In this way, practical language becomes essential. Culture is singular for communicative language instruction; Consequently, only what is appropriate for the interaction context is prioritized; this implies that the intercultural perspective is excused (Piatkowska, 2015). This issue might be raised because of the viewpoints taken on the English language. English is pronounced as the lingua franca because of its nearly 1,300,000,000 speakers worldwide (Ethnologue, n.d.). As a result, we should set the two perspectives apart: English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and EFL According to Fang (2017), although the majority of the EFL is concerned with teaching and learning British and American standard English, native English speakers are not considered to be superior in the ELF perspective.

The borders of the world are not opaque but are expanding; People live more connected lives as a result. Combined with the mechanical advancements and the open doors given by globalization, correspondence is quick and modest these days. The individuals are almost culturally, politically, and economically intertwined. Appropriately, applied phonetics reexamines the significance of learning and showing a language (Chamberlin-Quinslink and Senyshyn, 2012). If language teachers primarily focus on native language standards, will it be pedagogically relevant in this globalized world where English is the lingua franca? According to Baker's (2012) account, English's global position prevents it from being associated with any particular culture or nation. Whose culture does it represent if it is the universal language? The simple truth is that English is spoken generally by a larger number of people of the networks with various societies from one side of the planet to the other. In order to actively engage in cross-cultural communication, English language learners must have intercultural communication skills. It will be important to use the handle Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) Model, which was suggested by Byram (1997), to provide a comprehensive

understanding of the intercultural skills. There are five key competences in this model:

1. Knowledge: This connotes the information on friendly items, foundations, executions in any culture.
2. Communication and interpretation skills: The social executions are assessed and deciphered from the perspectives of that culture and afterward connected with one's source culture.
3. Abilities of revelation and connection: Through appropriate interaction, students can use these skills to acquire knowledge about other cultures.
4. Basic social mindfulness/Political instruction: The individuals evaluate the cultural implementations between the cultures using the explicit criteria.
5. Attitudes: To avoid stereotyping, one must use tolerance, empathy, and an open mind.

The significance of cultural awareness in English discourse had been acknowledged because this book mentioned that cultural awareness had emerged as one of the four essential components of English disciplinary core literacy. English course readings are significant asset in secondary school English educating, which is the extension to send the language information and the primary transporter to reflect social mindfulness.

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